

Rationale for Deception and Debriefing

To ensure the validity of the research data, it is necessary for participants to develop the flawed mental model without knowing that it is flawed. Otherwise, they might not display a genuine need for explanation when their flawed mental model conflicts with the system behavior. Therefore, participants should not be told that the tutorial material is erroneous before their session is completed.

After the experiment, participants have to be debriefed about the deception in order to ensure the ethical validity of the study. This should be done in accordance with the ethics board of the responsible research institution. An example of such a debriefing is provided below.

Debriefing Example: Explanation of the research question

The “Study with Citavi” is being conducted in connection with the “softXplain” research project. The Software Engineering group wants to investigate whether faulty mental models lead to a subjective need for explanation.

To ensure a faulty mental model, we showed you a video tutorial that intentionally contained errors. Based on the video alone, it would have been impossible to solve all provided tasks. Tasks 1.1 and 2.2 could be solved with the help of the video, but tasks 1.2 and 2.1 could not.

The video tutorial files located on the desktop contain correct explanations. If you are interested, you can now view them after completing the study. Thank you for your participation.